

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17469630>

ZOOSEMIZM TERMINING TADQIQOT BOSQICHLARI

U.S.Toirova

teacher of English Linguistics

u.s.toirova@bux.du

Introduction

Zoosemizm termini “zoo”-hayvon va semizm esa ma’no kabi ma’noni anglatadi.

Zoosemizm (hayvon metaforasi) terminini G.Stern, D.Uilkins, F.J.Tornton va G.A.Kleparski, Kardela va Kleparski Levandovska-Tomashchik ishlarida kuzatish mumkin.

G.Milichning ta’kidlashicha, *zoosemiyani* anglashda motivasion omillarni tahlil qilishning o’zi kamlik qiladi. J. Lakoff va M.Turnerlar *zoosemiya* terminini metaforalik xususiyatini sharhlab, metonimiyalik rolini e’tibordan chetda qoldirishadi, vaholanki, tabiatdagi har bir narsaning xalq nazdida metonimik ko‘rinishi ham mavjud².

G.Kleparskiy tadqiqotiga ko‘ra *equine, canine, feline* domenining semantik strukturasi quyidagilarni o‘z ichiga:

1. Domain of species – turlar domeni; Domain of functions – xatti-harakat domeni; Domain of origin/rank – nasl-nasab domeni; Domain of age – yosh domeni; Domain of character – xarakter domeni; Domain of behaviour and morality – xulq-atvor va ahloq domeni; Domain of physical characteristics and appearance – fizikaviy xususiyat va tashqi ko‘rinish domeni; Domain of abuse – kamsitish domeni.

²Kieltyka R. and Kleparski G.A. The scope of English zoosemy: The case of Domesticated Animals. –Poland: Studia Anglica Resoviensia, 3, 2005.– B.32.

A.Goatly fikriga ko‘ra, inson hayvondir semasini talqin qilinishining uchta usuli mavjud:

1. *Humans are part of the category animal*. Insonlar hayvon kategoriyasining bir qismidir. Ular giponim vazifasida ishlatiladi.

2. *Humans and animals are more or less alike*. Inson va hayvonlar ko‘p yoki kam darajada o‘xshash.

3. *Humans are like animals*. Inson hayvonga o‘xshaydi, degan metaforik ma‘noni bildiradi³.

Umuman olganda, J.Lakoff, M.Turner, G.Milichlarning izlanishlarida keltirilgan fikr-mulohazalar asosida *zoosemiya* ham metafora ham metonimiya vazifasida ishlatiladi, degan xulosa qilish mumkin.

G.Milich esa hayvonlarning ushbu subdomenlardagi eng ko‘zga ko‘ringan xususiyatlari keyinchalik insonning tashqi ko‘rinishi, intellekti, xarakteri va xulq-atvori bilan taqqoslanadi, asosiy xususiyatlar muhim xatti-harakatlarga olib keladigan narsalar tabiatining kognitiv modelida qo‘llaniladi, *xarakter* axloqning kengroq sohasi hisoblanadi, deb aytadi⁴. Demak, hayvon xususiyatining insonga qiyoslanishi ham *zoosemiyadir*.

F.Fontecha va J.Katalan ingliz (tulki/vixen, buqa/sigir) va ispan (zorro/zorra, toro/vaca) tillarida ikki juft hayvon so‘zlaridagi semantik derogasiyani o‘rganib chiqib, har ikki tilda bu so‘zlar ayollarga nisbatan ko‘proq ishlatilishiga ishora qiladi, deb aytishadi⁵.

Zoosemiya inson xususiyatlarini belgilash uchun qo‘llaniladigan hayvon nomlarining semantik o‘zgarish jarayonidir. B.Makvinney ta’kidlaganidek, inson bilan bog‘liq metaforalar hayvonlar xususiyatlari dunyosi va inson xususiyatlari dunyosi o‘rtasida o‘rnatilgan ma’lum bir izomorfizmga ishora qiladi.

³Goatly A. *Humans, Animals, and Metaphors* //– USA: Society & Animals, 2006. – №14(1). – P.15-37.

⁴ Egorova A. *Hunting down Animal Verbs: an Investigation into the Mechanisms of Meaning Transfer Underlying English Verbal Zoosemy*. – Potsdam, Germany: 2019. – P.24.

⁵ Lucija Kovačić *Zoosemy and Gender Stereotyping: A Corpus Analysis of Six Pairs of English and Croatian Lexemes*. Diploma thesis. – Zagreb. 2018. – P.20

R.Keiltika ingliz tilidagi zoosemiyalarni 1) kasbi va ijtimoiy funksiyasi; 2) xulqi va xarakteri; 3) ijtimoiy holati va kelib chiqishi; 4) jismoniy xususiyatlari va tashqi ko‘rinishi; 5) axloqi; 6) jinsi; 7) nafrat va tahqirlash kabi 7 ta kontseptual guruhga ajratadi⁶.

Xulosa

Demak, zoosemizmlar insonga metaforik ravishda ikkilamchi nom berish, shaxsni zoonimlar bilan atashni ifodalaydi va ular inson xarakter-xususiyatlarini ko‘rsatuvchi metaforalashgan zoonimlardan tashkil topadi. Ularning tilshunoslikdagi o‘rni va ishlatilishi turli tadqiqotlarda o‘z aksini topgan. Umuman olganda insonning xislatlarinig hayvon nomlari orqali metafora sifatida ishlatilishi tilshunoslikdagi eng dolzarb masalalrdan biri hisoblanadi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI:

1. Kiełtyka R. and Kleparski G.A. The scope of English zoosemy: The case of Domesticated Animals. –Poland: Studia Anglica Resoviensia, 3, 2005..– B.32.
2. Thornton F.J. A Classification of Semantic Field ‘Good and Evil’ in the Vocabulary of English. –UK: The University of Glasgow, 1989. – P.14.
3. Goatly A. Humans, Animals, and Metaphors //– USA: Society & Animals, 2006. – №14(1). – P.15-37.
4. Toirova U. S. Semantic determination of the noun //ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 11 (79). – 2019. – C. 139-143.
5. Toirova Umida Sobirovna. (2023). SHER ZOOSEMISM IN UZBEK WORKS. Web of Teachers: Inderscience Research, 1(8), 168–176. Retrieved from <https://webofjournals.com/index.php/1/article/view/345>

⁶Kiełtyka.R. Selected Aspects of Zoosemy: The Conceptual Dimension "Origin/Social Status". Philologia Hispalensis Project: The Semantic Scope of English Animal-Specific Surnames. –Poland: Rzeszów University. 2(24) December 2010. – pp. 167-189

6. Toirova, U. (2022). Analysing of Cat Zoosemy in the Uzbek and English Works. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/680411
7. Toirova, U. (2021). Maqollarda Zoosemizmlarning ingliz va o‘zbek tillaridagi ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 1(1). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/1953
8. Toirova Umida Sobirovna. (2023). THE DESCRIPTION OF LION ZOOSEMY IN UZBEK’S NOVELS. American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences, 11, 36–12. Retrieved from <https://americanjournal.org/index.php/ajrhss/article/view/580>
9. Umida Toirova, S. Ahmadning Qorako‘z Majnun va P. Turnering Nachiko hikoyalarida it zoosemasida sadoqat timsoli, ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz): Том 19 № 19 (2022): Статьи и тезисы (buxdu. uz)
10. Toirova U. Said Ahmadning “Qoplon” va Roald Dahl ning “Beware of the Dog” hikoyalarida It zoosemasi berilishi //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 8.
11. Toirova, Umida. "The interpretation of zoosemy through the symbol of Monkey in the stories of N. Eshonqul" "Maymun yetaklagan odam (The Man Leading the Monkey) and WW Jacob's "The Monkey's Paw" "Toirova Umida Sobirovna A teacher of English literature department Bukhara." ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz) 1.1 (2020).
12. Sobirovna T. U. O‘zbek Asarlarida Sher Zoosemizmi //Diversity Research: Journal of Analysis and Trends. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 50-57.